

First report from Sicily (Italy) of the orange spiny whitefly, *Aleurocanthus spiniferus* (Quaintance) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), and its potential risk for the Italian citrus industry

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Abstract

The orange spiny whitefly, *Aleurocanthus spiniferus*, is reported for the first time in the district of Catania, Sicily (IT). The pest was observed on ornamental sour orange trees cultivated along roads in the town of Catania as well as in commercial citrus orchards of the Plain of Catania. Italy is the second European citrus-producing country, after Spain, and more than 50% of Italian citrus are produced in Sicily, so the spread in this island of this new pest urgently requires adequate monitoring and control measures to protect this important crop.

Premier signalement de l'aleurode épineux du citronnier *Aleurocanthus spiniferus* (Quaintance) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) en Sicile (Italie) et le risque qu'il présente pour l'industrie italienne des agrumes

L'aleurode épineux du citronnier *Aleurocanthus spiniferus* est signalé pour la première fois en Sicile (IT), dans la province de Catane. L'organisme nuisible a été observé sur des orangers amers ornementaux plantés le long des routes dans la ville de Catane, ainsi que dans des vergers d'agrumes commerciaux dans la Plaine de Catane. L'Italie est le deuxième pays producteur d'agrumes en Europe après l'Espagne et plus de 50% des agrumes italiens sont produits en Sicile. La dissémination de ce nouvel organisme nuisible sur cette île nécessite donc, de toute urgence, des mesures de surveillance et de lutte adéquates afin de protéger cette culture importante.

Первое сообщение из Сицилии (Италия) о щетинистой цитрусовой белокрылке, *Aleurocanthus spiniferus* (Quaintance) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), и о потенциальном риске, который она представляет для итальянской отрасли производства цитрусовых

Щетинистая цитрусовая белокрылка *Aleurocanthus spiniferus* впервые обнаружена в районе Катания, Сицилия (Италия). Вредный организм был обнаружен на деревьях декоративных кислых апельсинов, выращиваемых вдоль дорог в городе Катания, а также в торговых цитрусовых садах на равнине Катании. Италия является второй после Испании европейской страной по производству цитрусовых, а более 50% итальянских цитрусовых производится на Сицилии. В связи с этим, распространение на этом острове этого нового

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вредного организма срочно требует надлежащего мониторинга и мер борьбы для защиты этой важной культуры.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Whiteflies (Hemiptera, Aleyrodidae) are among the main pests of citrus in Italy. All of them have been introduced over the last half century or so. In particular, six whitefly species have been recorded on citrus in Italy during the last three to four decades of the 20th century, namely *Aleurothrixus floccosus* (Maskell), *Bemisia afer* (Priesner & Hosny), *B. sp. gr. tabaci* (Gennadius), *Dialeurodes citri* (Ashmead), *Parabemisia myricae* (Kuwana) and *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (Westwood) (Rapisarda, 1990; Martin *et al.*, 2000). Two additional species, *Aleurocanthus spiniferus* (Quaintance) and *Paraleyrodes minei* Iaccarino, have been recorded during the current century (Porcelli, 2008; Jesu & Iaccarino, 2011; Cioffi *et al.*, 2013; Longo & Rapisarda, 2014).

One of the most recently introduced whitefly species, *A. spiniferus*, has spread very slowly after its first detection in 2008. Initially, its dispersal in Italy was limited to Apulia region, taking more than 5 years to spread west and north of the areas where it was first reported (Kenawy *et al.*, 2014). Apart from the Apulia region, *A. spiniferus* has been recorded very recently from the regions Basilicata, Campania, Emilia-Romagna and Latium, especially in urban areas and mainly on ornamental plants (EPPO, 2017, 2019; EFSA Plant Health Panel, 2018; Bariselli *et al.*, 2019).

Probably native to South-East Asia, where it is extremely widespread, *A. spiniferus* also occurs in other Asian countries such as Bangladesh, India, Iran, Pakistan and Sri Lanka, as well as in many countries in Africa and

Oceania, and in the Hawaiian Islands (USA) (Jansen & Porcelli, 2018; EPPO, 2021). In Europe, following its first finding in Italy (Porcelli, 2008), the orange spiny whitefly has also been recorded from Albania, Croatia, Greece and Montenegro (Šimala & Masten, 2013; Radonjić *et al.*, 2014; Šimala *et al.*, 2015; Kapantaidaki *et al.*, 2019; Nugnes *et al.*, 2020; EPPO, 2021).

Until now, the orange spiny whitefly, *A. spiniferus*, has never been recorded in either of the two regions (Calabria and Sicily) where almost 80% of Italian citrus cultivations are located. Therefore, the presence of *A. spiniferus* in Sicily, reported in this paper, presents a risk to the citrus industry in Italy.

2 | DIAGNOSIS

Identification of the spiny whitefly material collected in Sicily has been based on the morphology of its fourth-instar nymphs, prepared and mounted on slides as described by Rizzo *et al.* (2021) and observed by phase contrast microscope (Olympus BF51TF). Characters of the examined nymphs correspond to *A. spiniferus* and fall within its morphometric range, as stated by Jansen and Porcelli (2018).

3 | NOTES ON THE PEST

Adults of *A. spiniferus*, 1.3–1.7 mm long, can be easily recognized by their greyish colour, due to a wax powder coating over their light orange body. Nymphs are

FIGURE 1 Nymphs of *Aleurocanthus spiniferus* on the lower surface of a sour orange leaf (Catania, 24 December 2020) [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

flattened, oval in shape, black, with a white marginal waxy fringe; the fourth-instar nymph (puparium) is 0.8–1.3 mm long and 0.5–1.0 mm wide, typically with several pairs of long glandular spines characteristically arranged on the dorsum. Useful diagnostic features to discern both adults and nymphs of this species from other close representatives of the genus *Aleurocanthus* Quaintance have recently been provided by Kanmiya *et al.* (2011), Gillespie (2012), and Jansen and Porcelli (2018).

A. spiniferus is a highly polyphagous species, feeding on plants belonging to almost 40 families. Rutaceae of the genus *Citrus* are at serious risk to be threatened by this whitefly, which, however, tends to adapt very well to live on wild flora or on ornamental plants growing in urban areas, especially in newly colonized regions.

4 | FINDINGS IN SICILY

The first detection of *A. spiniferus* in Sicily was from the town of Catania, on the eastern coast of the island, where colonies of the whitefly (Figure 1) were noted in late December 2020, on some ornamental citrus trees cultivated along avenues and in squares, in mixed population with the Woolly whitefly, *A. floccosus*, and the black parlatoria scale, *Parlatoria ziziphi* (Lucas). Timely inspections carried out in citrus-growing areas of Eastern Sicily allowed detection of the insect in January 2021. Here it is already widely present and infesting citrus crops in the countryside of Caltagirone, in the plain of Catania (Eastern Sicily). An accurate investigation on the extent of diffusion of this whitefly in Sicilian citrus groves is needed urgently.

5 | PEST IMPORTANCE

Italy is the second most important citrus producer in Europe (after Spain), with about 140 000 hectares cultivated with citrus and an overall production of citrus fruits reaching almost 2.9 million tonnes in the year 2019 (FAOSTAT, 2021). Italian citrus production is mainly concentrated (with about 99% of the total national citrus-growing area) in its southern regions and in the two main islands, Sardinia and Sicily, especially in the latter one where 1.6 million tonnes of citrus are produced (e.g. more than 55% of Italian production), followed by the regions Calabria (765 thousand tonnes, almost 26% of national production), Puglia (193 thousand tonnes, about 7%), Basilicata (112 thousand tonnes, about 4%) and Sardinia (73 thousand tonnes, about 3%).

In this scenario depicting the extent of citrus cultivation among Italian regions and the significant economic importance of this crop in Sicily, the presence of a new whitefly among the pests threatening these important crops in this island requires adequate monitoring measures for its infestations and increasing actions to control and contain its spread in Sicilian citrus groves.

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